

What About the Energy-Efficiency of Complementary Services making a Fuel Cell Electrical Vehicle more Trustworthy and AI-Powered?

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Abstract— Fuel Cell Electric Vehicles (FCEVs) are a major development in environmentally friendly transportation because they produce only water as a waste when they generate energy using hydrogen fuel cells. By adding sophisticated complementary technologies, FCEVs can become more intelligent and trustworthy, which will increase their efficiency, performance, and overall user experience. Besides their advantages of energy saving and environmental friendliness, this article focuses not on the energy efficiency of electric vehicles themselves, but on the Artificial Intelligence (AI) and cyber security solutions that make them smarter and more trustworthy.

Keywords—Fuel Cell Electrical Vehicle, Artificial Intelligence, Cyber Security, Energy Efficiency

I. INTRODUCTION

The transport sector is a major source of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions globally, necessitating urgent measures to mitigate CO₂ and other GHG emissions across all transportation modes. The transportation, mobility and logistics sectors examine the potential impact of various zero-emission solutions, with a particular emphasis on clean hydrogen technologies. As evident from the market trends, Fuel Cell Electrical Vehicles (FCEV) will boom in the next few years. According to a recent review, the FCEV market was valued at USD 400 million in 2021, and it is expected to reach USD 8,500 million by 2027, with an estimated CAGR of around 30% during the forecast period (2022-2027) [1].

FCEVs utilize an electric motor powered by an electrochemical reaction between high-pressure hydrogen gas and oxygen within hydrogen fuel cells, producing electricity and water vapor. An FCEV contains a highly pressurized hydrogen tank, which releases gas to interact with the anode and cathode in the fuel cells. This interaction splits hydrogen molecules into protons (forming water) and electrons (generating electricity), which are then stored in a battery to power the motor. FCEVs offer several advantages, including the ability to refuel quickly, typically in just a few minutes, due to the efficient refueling process. They also provide a long driving range on a single tank of fuel and emit only water vapor, making them zero-emission vehicles. However, the limited number of refueling stations and

infrastructure issues make them less viable. Additionally, FCEVs are still expensive, and hydrogen production can be energy-intensive and often depends on non-renewable sources.

AI can address challenges in FCEVs by optimizing infrastructure, performing predictive maintenance, reducing costs, and improving hydrogen production. It enhances economic viability, and environmental monitoring, promoting widespread FCEV adoption. Additionally, robust cybersecurity is essential to protect FCEVs and related infrastructure against cyber threats through real-time threat detection, anomaly detection, automated incident response, and adaptive authentication (of both users and nodes). AI and cybersecurity ensure the efficient and secure operation of FCEVs in large-scale operations like public transport, fleet logistics, etc. Besides the advantages of energy efficiency and eco-friendliness of the FCEVs, this paper focuses on the energy cost of making them more AI-powered and trustworthy. As a case study, the authors calculated the energy consumed for AI-based predictive maintenance to monitor the State-of-Health (SoH) characteristics, analyze data, and predict potential failures before they occur. This approach schedules proactive maintenance, reducing downtime and repair costs, improving vehicle reliability, and enhancing safety. Additionally, the energy consumed for making an FCEV connected to third-party services is calculated to estimate the cost of making FCEV more resilient against cyber threats.

The organization of the paper is as follows: Section II presents the current state-of-the-art. Section III gives a brief overview of the FCEV architecture and potential contributions of complementary services that make an FCEV smarter and more secure. Then, Section IV introduces the experimental evaluation of the energy consumption of the cyber security and AI algorithms. Section V concludes the paper.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The widespread adoption of fuel cell vehicles in the market necessitates efficiency, a long lifecycle, and continuous health monitoring of key powertrain components. A recent review highlighted the health-aware energy management that tackles the prognostic, diagnostic and systemic energy management

strategies [2]. Condition monitoring has been reported as one of the key elements of smart FCEVs as model-based, filter-based or data-driven methods are used to predict failures and analyze the SoH throughout the life cycle of the vehicle [3]. Using the route information can help battery SoH in FCEVs, as proved in [4], such that the simulation results showed how the Hydrogen battery could be improved by addressing the predictive State-of-Charge (SoC) reference.

A digital twin (DT) adapted for prognostics can be viewed as a virtual representation of the health status of the physical system, an FCEV, or any related infrastructure, being studied, and equipped with sensors. A recent study classified the DT platforms and reported that data-driven DTs performed better than the model-based DTs due to their capabilities to handle complex systems in EVs [5]. A recent paper proposed a DT for a Fuel Cell Hybrid Electric Vehicle (FCHEV) to accurately model vehicle behavior and auxiliary systems during the Worldwide Harmonized Light Vehicles Test Procedure (WLTP) driving cycle [6]. The authors compared two control strategies—Range Extender and optimized Fuzzy Logic Control—to evaluate their effects on vehicle and component performance, emphasizing the energy impact on the Balance of Plant. A DT-based approach was developed for fuel cell degradation prediction in FCEVs [7]. The authors presented a hybrid technique that uses Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) as a transfer learning method enabling the DT to adapt to real-time operation conditions and parameter changes.

Figure 1. A typical high-level architecture of a connected and AI-powered FCEV (inspired from [11])

The energy efficiency of AI algorithms is a critical factor in the eco-friendliness of FCEV-based transportation solutions. The AI energy is often calculated in High-Performance Computing applications. A recent work investigated AI's environmental impact, focusing on energy consumption and CO2 emissions from machine learning algorithms [8]. It examined software, hardware, and energy source carbon intensity comparing various architectures for training the XGBoost, finding ARM-based systems to be a greener, viable alternative. It also shows that training Random Forest (RF) algorithms with low precision can reduce energy use without losing accuracy. Another paper provided a thorough assessment of training performance and energy consumption across diverse AI accelerators, such as Intel CPUs, AMD/NVIDIA GPUs, and Google TPUs [9]. It encompasses a wide range of deep learning tasks, including CNNs for image recognition, recurrent and non-

recurrent neural networks for translation, and Deep Speech 2 for speech recognition.

Current literature mentions that AI-based SoX estimation techniques present promising results. The integration of AI over DT platforms can tackle better condition monitoring, energy management and predictive maintenance. Despite their benefits, the energy consumption of AI-based tools is not negligible and should seriously be considered especially for heavy duty FCEVs or when the fleet of FCEVs is considered. The energy consumption of cyber security add-ons is usually underestimated as the existing literature focuses on CPU loads as an indicator of energy usage [10]. Hence, this paper's target is still a hot topic as there is a strong need to estimate the energy consumption of the complementary AI and cyber security services making a typical FCEV smarter and more trustworthy.

III. FCEV BACKGROUND

A typical FCEV is composed of two main parts: Fuel cell electric drive and EV power train, as depicted in Fig.1. FCEVs, more complex than traditional Battery Charging Electrical Vehicles (BCEV), can be likened to small hydrogen-fueled power stations and can travel approximately 400 miles on a full tank. The electric drive is composed of a fuel cell stack that consists of multiple fuel cells converting hydrogen and atmospheric oxygen into electrical energy through "cold combustion." This process requires a precise operating system to control the supply of hydrogen, oxygen, and moisture. Additionally, a cooling system regulates the stack's temperature. The fuel cell current measures the current density in the stack and determines the actual stack voltage, which must be measured synchronously. The stack voltage depends on the number of fuel cells. Even without power output, the stack has an open circuit voltage that is monitored during all test runs. The fuel cell-electric drive is a complete vehicle subsystem provided by suppliers, contributing to overall vehicle performance when combined with other powertrain components. Its characteristics and functions are verified through extensive testing before production. The energy from the fuel cell stack is directed to the DC/DC converter, which powers all high-voltage components and systems. This converter manages key functions, including setting the stack's setpoint current, and includes a boost converter to raise the voltage for the motor drivetrain and traction battery. The powertrain has DC/DC and DC/AC converters to drive the e-motor. In both electric drivetrain and powertrain, there exist specialized tools for state monitoring to observe temperatures, volumetric flows, humidity, and pressures, in addition to the measurements of currents and voltages in high-voltage circuits.

The Fuel Cell Electronic Control Unit (ECU) manages and optimizes the fuel cell system's performance and is connected to the drivetrain and powertrain over the CAN bus. ECU has a critical role and should be protected against unauthorized access. Among its functions, ECU monitors the fuel cell stack and components, controls the supply of hydrogen and oxygen, regulates the cooling system for optimal temperature, distributes electrical power to vehicle systems, detects and diagnoses faults, communicates with other vehicle control units, and manages different operating modes.

The FCEV is connected to the outer world via a secure CAN gateway which is coupled with a Hardware Security Module (HSM) that is installed on a server in the cloud. HSM is a master cryptographic device that is capable of true random number and crypto-key generation and one-time password creation, encrypting and decrypting with symmetric (e.g., 3DES, AES) and asymmetric (e.g., RSA) crypto-algorithms. Symmetric encryption is used for end-to-end two-way secure data exchange between the FCEV and the AI services on the cloud. Secure CAN gateway is an edge crypto device and utilizes the unique keys generated by the HSM. When the gateway is produced, it is coupled with the HSM and truly generated random numbers are filled in a secure memory on the gateway. The security operations of the gateway are managed by the HSM which makes the edge device (i.e., secure CAN gateway) dynamically resilient against cyber-attacks. Similarly, the CAN Authenticator (CANAT) is an on-demand hardware device that controls secure and authorized access to the FCEV CAN bus. Such an authentication mechanism is mandatory, especially during maintenance- as this device secures the CAN interface and prevents any unauthorized access to the CAN bus. CANAT is also coupled with the HSM as the required one-time passwords are generated by the HSM. HSM offers various security services, like Crypto-as-a-Service and Authentication-as-a-Service over the cloud that enables both person and node (FCEV in this case) authentication, key management and distribution, and data encryption, all of which present a holistic cyber shielding. TLS and other high-level cyber protection mechanisms strengthen the shielding mechanism.

The AI services over the cloud can be diversified according to the various needs of smart FCEVs. These services can be implemented as APIs over the cloud or modules of a DT. One can deploy a third-party AI service, for instance, to better observe and model the FCEV behaviors, route planning, energy management, monitoring, and prognostic health management. For the sake of proof of concept, three AI algorithms, Long Short-term Memory (LSTM), XGBoost, and RF are implemented in this study. The main purpose of these AI algorithms is to assess the health state of the fuel cells and estimate the Remaining Useful Life (RUL). The algorithms are selected as the widely adopted techniques that are used for prognostics and health management of an FCEV to improve the life cycle of the drivetrain and powertrain. The presented AI algorithms are trained by considering the saliency of parameters like stack temperature, hygrometry rates, inlet and outlet flow of hydrogen, air and cooling water, hydrogen and air pressure, gas humidification, single cell and stack voltages, and current values.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

The experiments aim to evaluate the energy consumption of AI and cyber security services that make an FCEV smarter and more resilient against cyber-attacks. For the cyber security evaluations, a typical hardware-based system is set up as

Figure 2. Experiment Setup

presented in Fig.2. The setup assumes that the FCEV is a secured black box all onboard systems are protected against tampering and any malicious manipulation. A J1939 OBD ECU Simulator mOByDic1700 [12] is used to simulate the physical connection to the CAN Bus of the FCEV. PRIGM Cyber Security Solution Family [13] specializes in the automotive domain. The solution family is composed of a CANAT (*PRIGM CANAT*), a secure CAN gateway (*PRIGM Midi-1*), and an HSM (*PRIGM Network HSM*). *PRIGM CANAT*, a crypto-supported authentication edge device is utilized for authorized access to the in-vehicle CAN network. *PRIGM CANAT* is integrated into the vehicle through specialized relay switches and enables authorized access to CAN data ports. *PRIGM Midi-1* is used as the secure CAN Gateway that enables secure data exchange between the FCEV and the cloud services. Both *PRIGM CANAT* and *PRIGM Midi-1* work in cooperation with the master crypto-device, *PRIGM Network HSM*, enabling active verification of edge devices on-demand.

The AI algorithms are tested on a PC with the following configuration: i) CPU: 12th Gen Intel(R) Core (TM) i7-12700H, 2300 Mhz, 14 Core(s), 20 Logical Processor(s), 24M Cache- up to 4.70 GHz; ii) RAM:16GB DDR5 2400 MHz; iii) GPU: GeForce RTX 3070 Laptop GPU 8GB GDDR6 256-bit. For the accuracy testing of the AI algorithms, the open datasets provided in IEEE PHM 2014 Data Challenge [14] are used.

A. Energy Consumption of AI Algorithms

Perun library [15], which is a de-facto tool that calculates the energy consumption of Python scripts, is used for LSTM, XGBoost, and RF algorithms with different numbers of CPU cores (single, double, and 4-core). Fig. 3 presents both accuracy and the consumed energy in terms of % and Joule, respectively. As expected, LSTM (Epochs: 100, Learning Rate: 0.03, Batch

Figure 3. Accuracy and energy consumption of selected AI algorithms

size: 32) is significantly less energy-efficient due to its sequential processing nature, and thus no significant change is observed as the number of CPU cores increases due to its limited parallelization benefits. On the contrary, both XGBoost (Learning rate: 0.1, N-estimator: 100, Max depth: 10) and RF (N-estimator: 50, Random state: 42) algorithms get more efficient with higher number of cores as this makes these algorithms more appropriate for parallel processing. The accuracy of XGBoost and LSTM does not dramatically change but a ~3% decrease is observed in the RF algorithm.

B. Energy Consumption of the Cyber Security Backend

The total energy consumption is measured by assuming that the FCEV is accessed via its CAN gateway for one hour and sends or receives 3 KB of vehicle and user data packages to/from the DT at each transaction. To measure the average power consumption of the *PRIGM Network HSM* and *PRIGM Midi-1 Secure Gateway*, initial data have been collected on both the idle and active power consumption state at a cryptographic service frequency of 3 Hz. Each cryptographic operation (RSA 2048 bit, SHA 256 bit, AES 256 bit) requires approximately 11.5 milliseconds, resulting in 34.5 milliseconds of active processing per second, which constitutes 3.45% of the total time per transaction. Subsequently, the weighted average power consumption was calculated by considering the system's behavior over 1 hour of activity followed by 1 hour of idleness. This methodology provides a comprehensive understanding of the system's power usage across different operational periods. *PRIGM CANAT* draws 50mA of current while in idle mode. Upon completion of cryptographic authentication processes, access to the CAN lines is facilitated by activating the relays and maintaining them in an active state. When the relays are open, the system draws a continuous current of 120mA.

TABLE I. ENERGY CONSUMED BY THE CYBER SECURITY HARDWARE AND SERVICES

Solution	Mode	Idle (without security services)	With security
PRIGM Network HSM		~35.1 Wh	~36.1 Wh
PRIGM Midi-1, Secure CAN Gateway		~5.0 Wh	~5.1 Wh
PRIGM CANAT, Can Authenticator		~1.2 Wh	~2.9 Wh
Total		~41.3 Wh	~44.1 Wh

The results show that the energy overhead of the cyber security countermeasures is about 6.7% for 3 transaction requests per second during a 1-hour operation. Note that this energy is negligible considering the FCEV's overall energy consumption at the scale of megawatts.

V. CONCLUSION

It is evident and obvious that AI and cyber security countermeasures enhance the cyber resilience and energy efficiency of FCEVs. This paper focuses on the energy cost of applying such complementary services by presenting a quantified approach calculated in Joules. The results show that algorithms having a sequential processing nature are more efficient, i.e. XGBoost and RF without any significant loss in accuracy as they are parallelized with a higher number of CPU cores. The results encourage authors to delve into deeper studies

to analyze the energy efficiency of other algorithms in different settings (e.g., not only in Intel or Nvidia as presented in this paper but also in other CPU architectures). Working on real data sets collected from test FCEVs is also planned for further steps where HPC infrastructures are also utilized for big data management, e.g., fleet logistics.

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